

Influence of User Interface Design Elements on Trust in Healthcare Artificial Intelligence Technologies: A Systematic Literature Review

Abdul-Hakeem Joosub¹ and Funmi Adebesein¹[0000-0003-0512-016X]

¹ Department of Informatics, University of Pretoria, Pretoria, South Africa
u22642006@tuks.co.za; funmi.adebesin@up.ac.za

Abstract. The adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies has seen a significant growth in the healthcare sector, catalysed by the COVID-19 pandemic. The integration of AI technologies into healthcare can accelerate the delivery of innovative and sustainable healthcare services, with potential benefits such as improved diagnostic accuracy, more efficient workflows, and reduced administrative workload for healthcare professionals. However, the successful adoption and continued use of healthcare AI systems can be influenced by users' trust. This study analysed and synthesised 24 peer-reviewed studies using a systematic literature review to derive four broad themes of user interface (UI) design elements that could influence users' trust in healthcare AI systems, namely, "Explainability and Transparency through UI Design", "Interface Modalities and Perception of Trust", "Managing Uncertainty and Risk in the Design of a UI", as well as "User Empowerment and Control through the UI". The findings suggest that user interface design is a fundamental determinant of trust in healthcare AI systems.

Keywords: User Interface Design, Healthcare AI Technology, Trust, Explainability.

1 Introduction and Background

The healthcare industry is often berated for its slow pace of digital transformation [1, 2]. This laggard status has been attributed to several factors, including privacy and security concerns [3]. The COVID-19 pandemic, despite its devastating effect, ironically accelerated the adoption of innovative digital technologies in the sector [4, 5]. One such innovation is the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into healthcare. There is no consensus on the definition of AI. However, one widely used definition is that it refers to a "machine" or computer program that exhibits human cognitive functions, including reasoning and decision-making [6]. The COVID-19 pandemic exposed weaknesses in the healthcare system, including insufficient healthcare personnel, poor infrastructure, and limited medical equipment/supplies [7]. The pandemic also catalysed the integration of AI technologies into healthcare systems [8], serving as a critical tool to curb the spread of the virus and for diagnostic purposes. Apell and Eriksson [9] argue that integrating AI technologies into healthcare can accelerate the delivery of innovative and

sustainable healthcare services. Some of the potential benefits of integrating AI into healthcare include improved diagnostic accuracy, more efficient workflows, and reduced administrative workload for healthcare professionals [8, 10]. Despite the highlighted benefits, the success of integrating AI into healthcare depends on users' trust [11]. Trust can be described as the willingness to be subjected to the results of the actions of another person (or thing), based on the expectation that the trustee will behave as expected by the trustor, regardless of whether the trustor has power to control the trustee's actions [12].

The design of the user interface (UI) can influence trust. Users' perceptions of the reliability and safety of healthcare AI technologies can be influenced by user interface features, such as transparency, explainability, and usability [13, 14]. Users' attitude towards healthcare AI systems can also be influenced by both cognitive and affective aspects of trust. According to Kulms and Kopp [15], the cognitive and affective aspects of trust, warmth (i.e., perceived positive intent), and competence (i.e., perceived capability) can influence users' willingness to adopt and use healthcare AI systems. In a study by Panigutti et al. [16], the authors noted that explainability and traceability can be facilitated by intentional UI design that enables users to comprehend and confirm AI decisions. Through co-design of a clinical decision support system, the authors demonstrated that a clear, contextualised explanation of AI decisions could lead to a high level of trust. Harrington and Egede [13] investigated trust among older Black Americans who use text-based healthcare chatbots. Their results showed that perceived trustworthiness depended on representation, professional appearance and conversational tone. Designs that match specific users' identities and values can also foster trust, particularly among the marginalised. Similarly, Degachi et al. [17] emphasise the importance of an appropriate level of trust that aligns with a system's real capacity, facilitated by open communication and ethical design processes. The design of basic UI elements, such as font size and avatar, can impact users' trust in AI systems [18].

Given the foregoing context, it is important to understand the UI elements that could contribute to users' trust in AI systems for healthcare. Consequently, the research question addressed in this paper is: *What interface design elements could influence trust in healthcare AI technologies?* It should be noted that this study did not focus on any particular AI application. The remaining sections of the paper are organised as follows: the research approach is explained in Section 2. This is followed by a highlight of the research findings in Section 3. Section 4 provides a detailed discussion of the themes and sub-themes derived from the analysis of the studies included in the research, while Section 5 concludes the paper.

2 Research Method

A Systematic Literature Review (SLR) was used in this study to analyse and synthesise extant research on the influence of interface design on trust in healthcare AI technologies. SLR is a process that allows for identifying, assessing and synthesising available studies on a particular topic or question [19]. The study followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guideline by Page et

al. [20]. Studies for the SLR were retrieved from four databases: ACM Digital Library, PubMed, Taylor and Francis, and Web of Science. The choice of these databases was intentional, as they cover a broad range of work in human-computer interaction, biomedical and clinical research, interdisciplinary scientific literature, and social sciences and communication. The search string used to determine applicable studies for inclusion in the SLR was ("healthcare artificial intelligence" OR "medical artificial intelligence" OR "healthcare ai" OR "medical ai") AND (trust OR credibility) AND ("interface design" OR "user experience" OR "ui/ux" OR "human-computer interaction" OR "user interface" OR "design principles"). The sources were retrieved between March and August 2025, using the inclusion and exclusion criteria in Table 1.

Table 1. Inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Peer-reviewed journal articles or conference papers	Studies that focused purely on algorithmic accuracy without user interaction context.
Studies published between 2020 and 2025.	Studies that focused on non-healthcare domains (e.g., AI in finance or education).
Studies that focused on trust in AI systems applied to healthcare.	Editorials, commentaries, or duplicate studies.
Studies that focused on interface design elements or user experience aspects applied in AI for healthcare.	
Full-text studies that are available in the English language	

A total of 340 records were retrieved from the databases (ACM = 248, PubMed = 13, Taylor & Francis = 70, Web of Science = 9). Ten duplicate records were deleted, leaving 330 unique records for screening. The titles and abstracts of the remaining 330 records were screened against the inclusion criteria in Table 1. This resulted in the exclusion of 197 records that were not relevant to answering the research question. These were studies that did not focus on trust, were not related to the healthcare domain, were review articles, or were highly technical articles that focused exclusively on algorithms. An additional 109 studies were excluded because they were not related to trust at the user interface design level, leaving 24 studies for inclusion in the SLR. The screening process is illustrated in Fig. 1.

The 24 research papers were analysed using quantitative descriptive statistics and qualitative content analysis.

Fig. 1. Source screening process.

3 Research Findings

The quantitative analysis revealed an increasing number of publications focusing on user interface design and trust in healthcare AI systems, with only one article in 2021, peaking at nine by August 2025, across the 24 studies that were analysed. Seventeen studies were journal papers, while the remaining were conference papers.

The qualitative content analysis yielded four broad themes, namely: (i) Explainability and Transparency through UI Design, (ii) Interface Modalities and Trust Perception, (iii) Managing Uncertainty and Risk in Interface Design, and (iv) User Empowerment and Control through UI. Within each theme, there were sub-themes. For example, the sub-themes "Visual Explanations", "Traceability via interaction design", and "User-centred explanations" were merged into the "Explainability and Transparency through UI Design" theme. A summary of the research findings is illustrated in Table 2.

Table 2. Summary of research findings.

Theme	Sub-theme	Citation	Number of studies
Explainability and transparency through UI Design	Visual Explanations	[14], [16], [21]	3
	Traceability via Interaction Design	[22], [23], [24], [25]	4
	User-centred Explanations	[14], [16], [23], [24], [26]	5
Interface modalities and trust perception	Text vs Speech vs Embodied Interfaces	[13], [27]	2
	Conversational Design	[26], [27], [28], [29], [30]	5
	Relational vs Functional Trust via UI	[13], [27], [29], [30], [31]	5
Managing Uncertainty and Risk in Interface Design	Confidence Indicators	[14], [21], [22], [28], [32], [33]	6
	Risk Communication	[17], [22], [32], [34], [35]	5

	Error Recovery Design	[14], [25], [30], [34]	4
User Empow- erment and Control through UI	Freedom to Choose / Human Alternatives	[17], [25], [35], [36], [37]	5
	Customisation and Personalisa- tion	[16], [28], [30], [31], [37], [38]	6
	Social Proof in Interface De- sign	[13], [36], [38]	3

The frequencies of the sub-themes derived from the 24 studies analysed show that not all interface design concepts were equally represented in the literature (see Table 2). The sub-themes "Confidence Indicators" and "Customisation and Personalisation" were derived from six studies, respectively. This is followed by the sub-themes "User-centred Explanations", "Conversational Design", "Relational vs Functional Trust via UI", "Risk Communication", and "Freedom to Choose / Human Alternatives", which were derived from five studies included in the SLR. "Traceability via Interaction Design" and "Error Recovery Design" were derived from four studies, respectively. The sub-themes "Visual Explanations" and "Social Proof in Interface Design" were derived from three studies, respectively. Lastly, the sub-theme "Text vs Speech vs Embodied Interfaces" was derived from two of the sources included in the SLR. A detailed discussion of the themes and sub-themes is provided in Section 4.

4 Discussion

4.1 Explainability and Transparency through User Interface Design

Explainability and transparency are measures of the extent to which users can understand the rationale behind the suggestions or decisions of healthcare AI systems. Clear explanations can help clinicians and patients in making informed decisions. The sub-themes under this section highlight the various design strategies that could support explainability and transparency in healthcare AI systems.

Visual Explanations. Interfaces that represent their reasoning graphically, for example, using highlighted features, contribution bars, and case-based comparisons, are more likely to engender the perception of competence and make trust calibration easier for users. The use of comparative visual risk displays and feature attributions can also assist users with interpreting model results during the screenings [21]. Authors such as Burgess et al. [14] and Panigutti et al. [16] recommend that the strength of evidence and visual justifications be displayed close to the AI system's recommendation to aid users' sense-making. Such designs allow users to transition from blind acceptance of an AI system's recommendations to understanding the reasoning behind the recommendation and informed decision-making.

Traceability Via Interaction Design. Trust is enhanced when decision trails can be inspected in the user interface, for example, through clickable evidence chains and audit

logs that show the data trail and model's steps. The embedding of traceability, logging and source links into an interface fosters a sense of an AI system that is accountable for its recommendations [23, 24]. Interaction design that supports traceability can be translated into user interface hints around data source, user confidence, and risk [22], as well as accountability-oriented explanations (rationales, checkpoints, review screens) that enable users to audit and challenge outputs. Hybrid human-AI workflows also require traceable handoffs and checkpoints on the UI to maintain a defensible record [25].

User-centred Explanations. Explanations that are configured around the user's role are more likely to be trusted. Such explanations take into account the user's AI literacy level and their objectives. Guidance should also prioritise matching content and appearance to the user's mental model [23, 24].

4.2 Interface Modalities through User Interface Design

The design of the interaction style, such as text, speech, or embodied interfaces, in healthcare AI systems is an important factor in shaping users' perception of a system's credibility and their trust in the system. The interface modalities can affect not only functional accuracy but also relational trust, since conversational trends and social cues can foster a sense of comfort and compassion. The sub-themes under this theme include the effect of modality selection and design attributes, including conversational design and relational versus functional trust via the user interface, on users' propensity to accept and trust AI healthcare systems.

Text vs Speech vs Embodied Interfaces. The modality of an AI system conveys a level of credibility. A study by Sun et al. [27] found that a text-based user interface was trusted more by users because this interaction modality supports scanning, re-reading, and cross-checking. Speech-based interfaces, on the other hand, were found to be the most convenient but less accommodating of users' mistakes, while embodied agents introduced additional ethical concerns around privacy and authenticity. In another study, Harrington and Egede [13] found that identity cues, attire, and representation had a moderating effect on comfort among black older adults, but did not necessarily engender trust when the source decision and privacy issues were unclear. Collectively, these findings indicate that modality selection should be combined with high levels of source transparency, and error-handling affordances should be implemented in healthcare AI systems.

Conversational Design. The ability to determine operational boundaries, request clarification, and negotiate the next steps in the interaction process can increase users' trust in text and voice-based user interfaces. Breuer et al. [26] underscore the importance of question prompts and tone in shaping engagements. The use of authentic language in chatbots and the expression of warmth can make conversations with a chatbot appear more benevolent (e.g. using emoji-supported microfeedback) [29]. Algarni [28]

recommends patient-centred assistants through the use of explain-back, teach-back responses, and step-by-step directions. Li et al. [30], on the other hand, recommend adjustable dialogue via modifiable dialogue settings (e.g., tone sliders, formality switches, etc.) to allow users to customise communication to their level of comfort, thereby preventing miscommunication between users and the AI system.

Relational vs Functional Trust via User Interface. Trusted interfaces can enhance functional and relational trust, including reliability, safety cues, warmth, and care signals [30, 31]. The personalisation of memory or micro-interactions, for example, the ability of an AI interface to convey the fact that it remembers the user, can engender relational trust [31]. A warm, authentic tone can also enhance the perception of altruism [29]. Authors like Harrington and Egede [13] and Sun et al. [27] found that users can differentiate between human-like trust and functional trust, with both driving acceptance. Hence, the user interface should use the appropriate social presence to foster transparency and reliability.

4.3 Managing Uncertainty and Risk in Interface Design

Some degree of uncertainty in medical decision-making is unavoidable. Hence, the communication of risk, as demonstrated by AI systems, can influence users' trust. The ability of a healthcare AI user interface to display confidence levels, potential errors and recovery mechanisms can assist users in making appropriate adjustments in their dependency on AI. The sub-themes within this theme include how confidence indicators, risk communication, and error recovery design can be used to manage uncertainty, promote transparency, and avoid over- or under-trust in healthcare AI systems.

Confidence Indicators. The level of trust in healthcare AI systems can be calibrated to reflect the model's confidence, the quality of the evidence and data coverage. Probability ranges and confidence labels can help users interpret risk predictions [21]. Burgess et al. [14] suggest that clinical advice should be designed by placing the evidence and confidence level in close proximity, e.g., side by side, to avoid over-reliance. User interfaces that express confidence, suggest a plan of action, and solicit feedback on verification can foster less-risky patient interaction [28]. A survey by Ojha et al. [32] revealed that users desire explicit uncertainties and evidence cues to be incorporated into the user interface to facilitate judgment of appropriateness.

Risk Communication. User interface designs that clearly communicate the potential risks associated with using healthcare AI systems are more likely to be trusted. Risk disclosure can be implemented via on-screen warnings, scope statements and links to evidence [22]. Building trust in healthcare AI systems requires that uncertainties be visible on the interface [17].

Error Recovery Design. Trust is preserved when user interfaces anticipate user errors and make recovery therefrom simple. There should be support for undo/override controls, clear handoffs to humans, and visible fallbacks. Wekenborg et al. [34] emphasised that escalation/override paths should be presented on workflow user interfaces. Explicit principles on how treatment decision support is to be achieved should include undo/override, second opinion and how to report issues [14]. Hybrid human-AI systems should also incorporate checkpoint sign-off disclosures and fail-safe defaults when uncertainties arise [25]. Conversational assistants should be able to prompt dialogic revisions and referral to clinicians when there is low confidence [30].

4.4 User Empowerment and Control through User Interface

Trust in healthcare AI systems can be fostered when users are empowered to make informed decisions and feel that they are in control of the decision-making process. AI systems that support personalisation and social proof can contribute to user acceptance and trust.

Freedom to Choose / Human Alternatives. Healthcare AI systems that preserve human agency, with opt-in, opt-out, ease of access to a human alternative, and visible override options, have a positive impact on attitudes and trust. Such interfaces support human-in-the-loop, with visible escalation mechanisms [17, 35]. A study by Alshakhsi et al. [36] found that users' freedom of choice can increase acceptance and, consequently, trust in the AI system, while another study by Kalving et al. [37] found that, in high-stakes contexts, professionals tend to prioritise human oversight and control over AI systems.

Customisation and Personalisation. Individualised content, saved preferences, and customisable explanation levels can make users feel that an AI system is designed with their needs in mind. This can engender relational trust and increase system utility [31]. In their study, Chen et al. [38] found that an AI system that supports personalisation is perceived as valuable, thereby increasing the perceived usefulness. Other researchers also found that healthcare AI systems with tools that allow users to adjust the tone and interaction style, as well as establish goals, are perceived positively by users, thereby fostering trust in the system [16, 28].

Social Proof in Interface Design. When designing for users with low literacy or novices, incorporating credibility cues and community validation into the user interface, for example, via badges, can enhance initial trust [36]. The authors found that incorporating social proof, for example, via clinician verification or peer usage indicators, can engender a positive attitude and user trust [36]. In another study by Harrington and Egede [13], the authors found that the perceived credibility of health chatbots was boosted by community involvement and endorsements among racial minorities, underscoring the importance of locally grounded social proof.

4.5 A Conceptual Model for User Interface Design Elements that Influence Trust in Healthcare Artificial Intelligence Systems

The analysis of the studies included in the SLR was further enhanced by developing a conceptual model that integrates the themes and sub-themes derived from the synthesis. The conceptual model (see Fig. 2) illustrates the links among design characteristics, user perceptions, and their influence on trust. Based on analysis of the 24 studies included in the SLR, there are four dimensions of user interface design: (i) explainability and transparency, (ii) interface modalities and trust perception, (iii) managing risk and uncertainty on the user interface, and (iv) user empowerment and control. The sub-themes constitute the interface design elements that can be practically implemented to engender user trust across the four dimensions. These design dimensions directly shape users' perception and trust in healthcare AI systems. User perceptions act as mediators, illustrating how the UI design characteristics translate into trust. The conceptual model illustrates the vital role of trust in shaping successful adoption of healthcare AI systems through adoption and continued use, user satisfaction and engagement, and appropriate trust (neither excessive nor insufficient reliance on the system).

Fig. 2. Conceptual model for user interface elements that influence healthcare AI system trust

5 Conclusion

This paper presents the results of a systematic literature review that investigates the user interface design elements that could influence users' trust in healthcare AI systems. Twenty-four peer-reviewed studies were analysed and synthesised to answer the research question: *What interface design elements could influence trust in healthcare AI technologies?* The findings suggest that user interface design is a fundamental determinant of trust in healthcare AI systems. The success of AI in healthcare is not limited to

the accuracy of algorithms but also how information is conveyed, contextualised and made actionable through design interventions.

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